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Studies on Basic Lead Sulphate Ion-exchanger. Part-I. Synthesis, Properties, Anion-exchange Behaviour and Separation of Anions

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THIS paper reports the synthesis, composition, chemical and thermal stability, pH-titration and anion-exchange behaviour of basic lead sulphate. Distribution and separation of various anions have been studied. No such study on basic lead sulphate has been reported earlier.

Experimental

Basic lead sulphate: Four different batches (B_1 , B_2 , B_3 and B_4) of basic lead sulphate were prepared by mixing $0.5M$ $Pb(NO_3)_2 + 0.5M$ $Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O / (NH_4)_2SO_4$ and $0.5M$ NH_4OH in different ratios and refluxing for different time periods. $Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$ was used for B_1 while for the others $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ was used. The refluxing time for B_1 was 4 h and the product was allowed to stand for 24 h, filtered, washed with deionised water (pH 6.5), dried at room temperature and finally at $100 \pm 5^\circ$ for 1 h.

Lead and sulphate were then estimated by titration with standard EDTA solution¹. The water molecules present in basic lead sulphate were determined as before². The weight loss (%) at 600° were 4.7 (B_1), 4.0 (B_2), 2.0 (B_3) and 1.4 (B_4). No further weight loss occurred on heating upto 800° . The ratio of $Pb : SO_4 : H_2O$ in the products were found to be (B_1) 2 : 1 : 1.4, (B_2) 2 : 1.7 : 1.2, (B_3) 2 : 1.6 : 0.6 and (B_4) 2 : 1.6 : 0.5. The exchangers were stable towards $2.0M$ H_2SO_4 , $0.01M$ HCl , HNO_3 , CH_3COOH and $HClO_4$ and $0.1M$ $NaOH$ and NH_4OH . For column operation, 5.0 g of the exchanger in a glass column (1.1 cm i.d.) was used. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Results and Discussion

Plots of pH against volume of added acid showed two sharp breaks³ indicating bifunctional nature of the basic ion-exchangers.

Ion-exchange capacity: The exchange capacity was determined by batch operation⁴. A constant exchange capacity was obtained for sodium chloride solution of concentration greater than $1.0M$ for which complete equilibration required 4 h. The total exchange capacity was determined at different pH by taking 0.5 g of exchanger and either 200 ml of $1M$ ($HCl + NaCl$) or $0.5M$ ($H_2SO_4 + Na_2SO_4$) with varying quantities of acid. The chloride ion-exchange capacities (meq/g) for B_1 at different equilibrium pH were 0.7 (pH 5.0), 1.7 (pH 4.4), 2.5 (pH 4.0), 2.9 (pH 3.5), and for sulphate ion the exchange capacities were 0.9 (pH 4.0), 1.2 (pH 3.4) and 2.8 (pH 3.3) indicating increases of exchange capacity with decrease of pH. Slight decrease from 2.77 to 2.55 meq/g in anion-exchange capacity was observed when heated upto 300° , but when heated to 600° the exchange capacity decreased to 1.0 meq/g. Regeneration capacity for SO_4^{2-} after 2nd regeneration was found to be 2.0 meq/g.

Column elution of hydroxyl ion: Column elution study⁵ using 0.5 and 0.05 M Na_2SO_4 in $0.05 M$ H_2SO_4 reveals that the amounts of hydroxyl ion released from the first two or three fractions were greater than those from the later fractions, because all the exchangeable ions were in hydroxyl form at the beginning. Almost all the hydroxyl ions were released completely after passage about 50 ml of the eluant.

Distribution coefficient (K_d): The apparent distribution coefficient (Table 1) of anions were determined at two different pH ranges 3.0-3.5 and 5.5-6.0 by batch operation⁶ using 0.5 g of exchanger (B_1) and (B_2) and keeping the anion concentration $3-3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$. The anions were estimated volumetrically^{1,6}. Phosphate was estimated spectrophotometrically⁷.

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS (K_d) OF ANIONS ON BASIC LEAD SULPHATE (B_1 AND B_2)

Anions	K_d at pH 3.0-3.50		K_d at pH 5.50-6.0	
	B_1	B_2	B_1	B_2
CrO_4^{2-}	2.9×10^3	2.3×10^3	2.6×10^3	2.4×10^3
VO_4^{3-}	76.0	11.0	—	—
PO_4^{3-}	1.6×10^4	458.0	4.1×10^3	9.5
AsO_4^{3-}	97.0	62.5	72.5	64.2
AsO_3^{3-}	131.1	79.3	89.1	73.0
$Fe(OH)_4^{3-}$	1.1×10^3	580.0	580.0	385.7
$Fe(OH)_3^{2-}$	12.0	10.8	3.3	2.9
SCN^-	7.0	5.0	5.0	3.7
$Br(v)$	13.4	7.5	7.5	4.7
$I(v)$	3.3×10^3	1.1×10^3	200.0	256.8
$C_2O_4^{2-}$	836.0	1070.0	367.0	175.3
MnO_4^-	9.8	8.7	—	—

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Chromate, phosphate, ferrocyanide, iodate and oxalate having very high K_d values could be sepa-

rated from vanadate, ferricyanide, thiocyanate, bromate, permanganate, etc. having of lower K_a values. The selectivity scale for B_1 at pH 3.0–3.5 was found to be $BrO_3^- < IO_3^-; SCN^- < [Fe(CN)]_6^{3-} < [Fe(CN)]_6^{4-}; MnO_4^- < VO_3^- < AsO_4^{3-} < AsO_3^{3-} < CrO_4^{2-} < PO_4^{3-}$. At higher pH, CrO_4^{2-} was more selective than PO_4^{3-} for B_3 .

Ion-exchange separation: Taking advantage of the differences in K_a values the following separations have been achieved (specific eluate volumes are given in the parenthesis): thiocyanate (20 ml of dilute HNO_3 , pH 3.5) from chromate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4), arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4), phosphate (25 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4), vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4), ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 M H_2SO_4), arsenite (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4) and iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4 in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4); chromate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4) from permanganate (20 ml of dilute HNO_3 , pH 3.5), ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 M H_2SO_4), bromate (20 ml of dilute HCl, pH 3.5), iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4 in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4), phosphate (25 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4), and vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4); ferricyanide (20 ml of dilute HCl, pH 3.5) from ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 M H_2SO_4), iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4 in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4), phosphate (25 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4), arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4), chromate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4), vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4); permanganate (20 ml of dilute HNO_3 , pH 3.5) from iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4 in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4), arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4) and vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4); bromate (20 ml of dilute H_2SO_4 , pH 3.5) from phosphate (25 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4), iodate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4 in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4) and arsenate (25 ml of 0.05 M H_2SO_4); vanadate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4) from ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 M H_2SO_4) and phosphate (25 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4); and oxalate (25 ml of 0.0025 M H_2SO_4 in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4) from ferrocyanide (25 ml of 0.36 M H_2SO_4) and phosphate (25 ml of 1 M H_2SO_4).

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One-step Synthesis of Steroidal Lactams from Ketones of Spirostane Series

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THE Beckmann rearrangement of steroidal ketoximes and Schmidt reaction of steroidal ketones are the usual methods to obtain steroidal lactams¹. Olah and Fung² reported the synthesis of lactams in one-step from alicyclic ketones by the action of hydroxylamine-*O*-sulphonic acid (HOSA) in hot formic acid. We now report the formation of lactams from steroidal ketones of spirostane series by the aforesaid method.

(25*R*)-5-Spirosten-3 β -ol (diosgenin; **1a**) on reaction with thionyl chloride in benzene solution at room temperature afforded 3 β -chloro-(25*R*)-5-spirostene (**1b**). The reduction of **1b** with sodium in isopentanol furnished (25*R*)-5-spirostene (**1c**). The chromic acid oxidation of **1b** and **1c** in glacial acetic acid after usual workup afforded their respective α,β -unsaturated ketones (**2b** and **2a**). The α,β -unsaturated ketone (**2c**) was prepared according to the method by Singh and Padmanabhan³.

The steroidal ketones (**2a–c**) were subjected to the action of HOSA in hot formic acid (60–70°) in the nitrogen atmosphere for 2 h and after usual workup the lactams (**3a–c**) were obtained in good yields (60%). However, if reaction with the same reagent (HOSA) was carried out at room temperature for 30 min in an atmosphere of nitrogen it gave the respective intermediate oxime-*O*-sulphonic acids (**2d–f**). The oxime-*O*-sulphonic acids (**2d–f**) on keeping over a column of neutral alumina followed by chromatography (Craig's procedure⁴) afforded the lactams (**3a–c**).

The lactams (**3a–c**) were also prepared by the Beckmann rearrangement of ketoximes (**2g–i**) using *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (PTS) in pyridine to form oxime tosylates, which on keeping over a column of neutral alumina followed by chromatography⁵ gave the lactams (**3a–c**). The lactams obtained by the above two methods are identical in all respects (ir, m m.p. and co-tlc). Their spectral data are comparable with that of (25*R*)-7*a*-aza-7-oxo-*B*-homo-5-spirosten-3 β -yl acetate^{3,4}.

The lactam (**3a**) on catalytic hydrogenation using Pd/C in absolute methanol gave the saturated lactam (**4**); tlc in benzene–ether (1:2) showed single spot; ν_{max} 3 200 (NH) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (CONH); δ 5.5 (1H, s, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 3.5 (1H, m, 8 β -H) and 1.6 ($C_{10}-CH_3$); λ_{max} 240 nm.